
A Meta-Analysis Of The Influence Of Incorporating Practical Activities Into Physics Lessons In Senior High Schools In Ghana

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ARTICLE INFORMATION

ABSTRACT

Volume: 4
Issue: 2 | 2022
DOI:10.5281/zenodo.7301735

KEYWORDS

Incorporation, physics teachers, practical activities, science teaching.

Nurturing scientific curiosities in learners is inconceivable if theory is not linked to practice in the teaching and learning process as enshrined in the physics teaching syllabus for Ghanaian senior high schools. Undeniably, practical activities facilitate how learners generate, acquire, and become proficient of scientific knowledge, competencies, processes and values in well-organised and productive ways. This work is guided by research questions: "Why do physics teachers incorporate practical activities into their lessons in senior high schools?" and "What are the impacts of incorporating practical activities into physics lessons in senior high schools?" As a result, a meta-analytical assessment of related literature was carried out to provide refreshing insight on the influence of incorporating practical activities into physics lessons. Important issues emanating from the review of related literature include need for pedagogical practical experiences, adoption of appropriate pedagogical strategies linking theory and practice, and impact of practical activities on learning outcomes.
